

Voltammetric Determination of Niclosamide

C. SRIDEVI and S. JAYARAMA REDDY*

Department of Chemistry, S. V. U. College of Engineering,
Tirupati-517 502

Manuscript received 9 February 1990, revised 7 January 1991, accepted 8 May 1991

The electrochemical behaviour of niclosamide is described on the basis of the study carried out using d.c. polarography, cyclic voltammetry, a.c. polarography and differential pulse polarography in the supporting electrolytes of pH ranging from 2.0 to 12.0. A tentative mechanism for the reduction of niclosamide is proposed that involves the transfer of $4e^-$. Parameters such as diffusion coefficients and heterogeneous forward rate constant values are evaluated. A differential pulse polarographic method has been developed for the quantitative determination in different pharmaceutical formulations using method of standard addition.

NICLOSAMIDE (2,5'-dichloro-4'-nitrosalicylanilide), an anthelmintic agent¹, is a halogenated salicylanilide derivative.

The electrochemical reduction of nitro group containing compounds at the dropping mercury electrode in aqueous solutions is described by Shikata and co-workers^{2,3}. Polarographic behaviour in aqueous systems has been reviewed by Kolthoff and Lingane⁴ and a number of papers have been published on nitro aromatic reductions following the early work of Geske and Maki⁵. A survey of the literature reveals that no attempt has been made to study the electrochemical reduction behaviour of niclosamide using advanced electrochemical techniques, such as d.c. polarography, cyclic voltammetry, a.c. polarography and differential pulse polarography as well as its determination in pharmaceutical preparations by using any analytical methods. Reported in the paper are the results of studies carried out on the electrochemical reduction behaviour of niclosamide in aqueous buffer media, so as to arrive at information on the mechanistic aspects and the electrode kinetics concerned. Also, attempt has been made to determine quantitatively the title compound in pharmaceutical formulations by differential pulse polarography without any prior separation.

Experimental

The details of the equipment used for the four different electroreduction techniques mentioned have all been described elsewhere⁶. The dropping mercury electrode used had the following characteristics: area = 0.0223 cm², drop time = 2 s, hanging mercury drop electrode (HMDE) had an area = 0.02323 cm².

Niclosamide (A.R., Biddle Sawyer) was used as such and its stock solution was prepared in double-distilled dimethylformamide. The supporting electrolytes (pH 2.0–12.0) were prepared using 0.2 M boric acid, 0.05 M citric acid and 0.1 M

trisodium orthophosphate. All the chemicals used are of AnalaR grade and the solutions were prepared using triple-distilled water. The test solutions of desired concentration were prepared by mixing the stock solution with supporting electrolyte and deaerated with O₂-free nitrogen gas.

Results and Discussion

Niclosamide is found to be voltammetrically reducible in a single step over the whole pH range 2.0–12.0, the nitro group getting reduced to the hydroxylamine group in a four-electron process (Figs. 1–4). A small anodic peak *a*₁ has been noticed in reverse scan of a cyclic voltammogram in alkaline solutions (pH ≥ 8.0). In the second

Fig. 1. Typical d.c. polarogram of niclosamide at pH 4.0; concentration = 0.5 mM and drop time = 3 s.

scan, another small cathodic peak C_2 at a more positive potential than C_1 is noticed (Fig. 2). The anodic peak may be ascribed to oxidation of the reduced product at C_1 ($R-NHOH \rightarrow R-NO + 2e^- + 2H^+$) and the cathodic peak C_2 to the reduction of the oxidised product at a_1 ($R-NO + 2e^- + 2H^+ \rightarrow R-NHOH$). This redox couple is noticed to be irreversible as evidenced from the separation of their E_p values.

Fig. 2. Typical cyclic voltammogram of niclosamide at pH 12.0; concentration = 0.5 mM and scan rate = 40 $mV s^{-1}$.

The electrode process is found to be diffusion-controlled in all the buffer systems studied, as shown by the linear dependence of limiting current on $h^{1/2}$ and concentration (Fig. 5). All these plots are observed to be passing through origin indicating

Fig. 3. Typical a.c. polarogram of niclosamide at pH 10.0: (a) a.c. peak, (b) base line; concentration = 0.5 mM and drop time = 3 s.

the absence of adsorption complications. The experimental constancy of $i_p/Cv^{1/2}$ with scan rate (v) has shown the electrode process to be free from any kinetic complications. When the concentration of the niclosamide increases, the half-wave/peak potential values are found to change to more negative values. This phenomenon is the characteristic feature of irreversible process. The variation of peak potential from -0.23 to -0.34 V vs Ag/AgCl (s) Cl^- for a change in scan rate of 40 to 800 mVs^{-1} at pH 4.0 in cyclic voltammetry as also the non-linearity exhibited by the plot of i_m vs $(1-\sigma)/(1+\sigma)$ are also indicative of the above fact. The plots of $E_{1/2}$ vs $\log i/(i_a-i)$ in various supporting electrolytes are found to be linear but their slopes as well as non-compliance of Tomes' criterion confirm the irreversible nature of the electrode process.

Fig. 4. Typical differential pulse polarogram of niclosamide at pH 6.0; concentration = 0.5 mM and drop time = 2 s.

The half-wave/peak potential values of niclosamide are found to be pH-dependent and shifted cathodically indicating proton involvement in the electrode process. The half-wave/peak potential values of the reduction wave are shifted to more negative potentials with increase in pH. An increase in the percentage of DMF in the polarographic test solution is seen to shift the half-wave potential with simultaneous decrease in diffusion current. These effects may be ascribed respectively to a decrease in surface concentration of the depolariser and an increase in the viscosity of the medium with an increase in the percentage of the non-aqueous solvent in the aqueous organic mixture⁷. A decrease in surface concentration would retard the electrode process resulting in a decrease in half-wave/peak potentials and diffusion current/peak current⁸. From the slope of the linear plot of

$E_{1/2}$ vs pH (not shown) and utilising the equation,

$$\Delta E_{1/2} / \Delta \text{pH} = \frac{-0.059P}{\alpha n_a}$$

where $\Delta E_{1/2}$ is the difference in half-wave potentials, ΔpH the difference in pH, α the transfer coefficient, n_a the number of electrons involved in the rate determining step, and P the number of protons involved in rate-determining step, the number of protons in the rate-determining step is found to be one, assuming $\alpha=0.453$.

The total number of electrons involved in the reduction process of niclosamide is found to be four at pH 2.0 and pH 12.0 as determined by millicoulometry. Controlled potential electrolysis has been carried out at pH 2.0 and 12.0 at potentials -0.15 and -0.60 V vs SCE and the reduction product is isolated and identified by its spectra as the corresponding hydroxylamine which is also supported by the cyclic voltammetric experiments. In cyclic voltammetry, an anodic peak is found to be observed in the first reverse scan which may be attributed to the oxidation of hydroxylamine formed at the

electrode surface to nitroso group⁹. Formation of nitroso and hydroxylamine couple also gives support for the contention that hydroxylamine is the final product under the experimental conditions (Fig. 2).

Kinetic parameters such as diffusion coefficient and heterogeneous forward rate constant values are evaluated (Table 1). The diffusion coefficients calculated from different techniques are seen to be in good agreement, indicating the diffusion-controlled and adsorption-free nature of the electrode process. The reason for the slight variation in the diffusion coefficient values with increase in pH may be attributed to the decrease in the availability of protons with increase in pH of the supporting electrolyte. The heterogeneous forward rate constant values in general are found to decrease with increase in pH indicating that the electrode reaction tends to become more and more irreversible. In acidic solutions when $k_{f,h}^0$ values are high, proton involvement is high which makes the protonated species to reduce readily and easily. But in alkaline solution when the $k_{f,h}^0$ values are low the reduction of nitro group does not occur easily owing to the non-availability of protons. The rate constant (k_s) values obtained in a.c. polarography are found to be high when compared to other techniques. The rate constants are evaluated at standard potentials in a.c. polarography while these are calculated at potential $E=0$ in other techniques.

Based on the results the mechanism presented in Scheme 1 can be suggested for the voltammetric reduction of niclosamide.

Fig. 5. Plots of i_d vs C of niclosamide at different pH: (a) 2.0, (b) 4.0, (c) 6.0, (d) 8.0, (e) 10.0, (f) 12.0; concentration = 0.5 mM.

Scheme 1

TABLE 1—TYPICAL ELECTRODE KINETIC DATA OF NICLOSAMIDE

Concentration = 0.5 mM pH of supporting electrolyte	D.C. Polarography Drop time : 3 s			Cyclic voltammetry Scan rate : 40 mV s ⁻¹			A. C. Polarography Drop time : 3 s			Differential pulse polarography Drop time : 2 s		
	$-E_{1/2}$ V	$D \times 10^5$ cm ² s ⁻¹	$k_{f,h}^0$ cm s ⁻¹	$-E_p$ V	$D \times 10^5$ cm ² s ⁻¹	$k_{f,h}^0$ cm s ⁻¹	$-E_s$ V	$D \times 10^5$ cm ² s ⁻¹	k_s cm s ⁻¹	$-E_m$ V	$D \times 10^5$ cm ² s ⁻¹	$k_{f,h}^0$ cm s ⁻¹
	2.0	0.10	2.49	6.18×10^{-4}	0.09	2.51	7.83×10^{-4}	0.11	2.45	6.92×10^{-2}	0.08	2.38
4.0	0.24	2.32	1.20×10^{-5}	0.23	2.38	5.19×10^{-6}	0.25	2.28	1.12×10^{-3}	0.23	2.26	6.98×10^{-5}
6.0	0.29	2.19	4.77×10^{-8}	0.30	2.15	8.34×10^{-7}	0.31	2.10	5.94×10^{-6}	0.29	2.07	5.01×10^{-6}
8.0	0.35	2.08	8.54×10^{-7}	0.37	2.09	3.81×10^{-7}	0.37	2.01	9.98×10^{-6}	0.36	1.97	1.37×10^{-6}
10.0	0.42	2.01	1.35×10^{-9}	0.43	1.93	8.12×10^{-9}	0.44	1.97	6.40×10^{-6}	0.43	1.92	2.89×10^{-6}
12.0	0.53	1.98	5.43×10^{-10}	0.53	1.95	6.67×10^{-10}	0.54	1.83	5.55×10^{-7}	0.52	1.83	8.65×10^{-10}

Analysis: Differential pulse polarography is used for the analytical determination of niclosamide adopting both calibration and standard addition methods. The polarographic peak obtained in the pH zones $4.0 \leq \text{pH} \leq 8.0$ is well-resolved and may be utilised for the analysis experiments. Linear calibration plots are obtained over the concentration range of 2.5×10^{-5} to $2.5 \times 10^{-7} M$.

Recommended analytical procedure: A $1.5 \times 10^{-5} M$ standard solution is prepared by dissolving the required quantity of niclosamide in DMF. A 1 ml of standard solution is placed in a polarographic cell and is made up to 10 ml with the supporting electrolyte and then deaerated with O_2 -free nitrogen gas for 10 min. After recording the polarogram, small increments (0.2 ml) of the standard solution is added, and after deaeration for 1 min, the polarogram is again recorded under similar conditions; 10 polarograms are recorded for 10 standard additions. Concentration of the sample solution is calculated by using the equation,

$$C_u = \frac{C_s \times V}{V_t \times i_2} \times i_1$$

where i_1 is the observed maximum current (μA) of differential pulse polarogram of the unknown solution, i_2 the maximum current (μA) of differential pulse polarogram after adding a volume of known concentration, C_s the concentration of standard solution (mM), C_u the concentration of unknown solution (mM) and V_t the total volume of the solution ($V+v$).

The results are found to be accurate and reproducible. The relative standard deviation and correlation coefficient are found to be 2.7% and 0.989 respectively. The optimum conditions for the analytical determination of niclosamide in pH 4.0 is found to have a drop time of 2 s and pulse amplitude of 60 mV at an applied potential of $-0.23 V$ vs $Ag/AgCl(s), Cl^-$.

The procedure is successfully employed for the determination of niclosamide in pharmaceutical formulations without any prior separation. The tablet (Vomensan) containing niclosamide was analysed in different buffered solutions (pH 4.0–8.0) using the above mentioned procedure. The results are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2—ASSAY OF NICLOSAMIDE BY DIFFERENTIAL PULSE POLAROGRAPHY

Pulse amplitude=60 mV, Drop time=2 s				
pH of supporting electrolyte	Amount labelled mg	Amount found mg	Recovery %	Standard deviation
4.0	500	499.00	99.80	0.015
6.0	500	498.95	99.75	0.018
8.0	500	499.80	99.96	0.023

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

References

1. W. E. JONES, *Am. J. Trop. Med. Hyg.*, 1979, 28, 300.
2. M. SHIKATA, *J. Agric. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1925, 1, 53¹.
3. M. SHIKATA and M. HOZAKI, *Mem. Coll. Agric., Kyoto Imp. Univ.*, 1931, 1721.
4. I. M. KOLTHOFF and J. J. LINGANE, "Polarography", 2nd. ed., Interscience, New York, 1952, pp. 652, 699.
5. D. H. GESKE and A. H. MAKI, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 82, 2761.
6. K. V. REDDY and S. J. REDDY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect A*, 1986, 25, 223.
7. S. G. MAIRANOUSKII and V. P. GULTGAI, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1965, 63, 5778.
8. P. ZUMAN, "The Elucidation of Organic Electrode Process", Academic, New York, 1969.
9. P. T. KISSINGER and W. R. HEINEMANN, *J. Chem. Educat.*, 1983, 60, 702.